

GroMiT
Planet *Growth & Migration* Track Code

User Manual
Version 1.0.1

Danae Polychroni¹, Diego Turrini^{2,3,4}, Simona Pirani

¹INAF-OATs, Via G.B. Tiepolo 11, I-34143, Trieste, Italy

²INAF-OATo, Via Osservatorio 20, I-10025, Pino Torinese, Italy

³INAF-IAPS, Via Fosso del Cavaliere 100, I-00133, Rome, Italy

⁴ICSC – National Research Centre for High Performance Computing, Big Data and Quantum Computing, Via Magnanelli 2, I-40033,

Casalecchio di Reno, Italy

email: danae.polychroni@inat.it

Index

Abstract	3
1. Introduction	3
1.1 Scope.....	3
1.2 Planet Formation.....	3
2. Software description	5
2.1 Python Modules required.....	6
2.2 Version.....	6
2.3 Licence.....	6
2.4 Usage.....	6
2.4.1 <i>Run GroMiT in an IDE</i>	6
2.4.2 <i>Run GroMiT in a Python console</i>	7
2.4.3 <i>Set the Initial Parameters</i>	7
2.4.4 <i>Library of Constants</i>	10
2.4.5 <i>Auxiliary Equations Used</i>	10
2.4.6 <i>GroMiT.py</i>	11
3. History	12
4. Bibliography	13
5. Acknowledgements	13

Abstract

In this report we document the Python program **GroMiT**. GroMiT resolves over time the mass growth of a planet in a circumstellar disk through pebble and gas accretion as well as tracks its migration through the host disc during a user defined temporal interval. In the following we concisely describe the physics and the equations used in the program. Finally, we document and describe the input parameters as well as how to use the program and its resulting output.

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope

In this document we provide a user guide for GroMiT, the planet growth and migration tracks program developed in Python 3 as part of the Arxes suite of codes at INAF. GroMiT calculates the migration and growing mass of a forming planet as a function of the local characteristics of its native circumstellar disk, whose global properties are set by the user. We provide a synthetic overview of the theory of planet formation through pebble accretion on which this software is based on and the relevant bibliography. We then describe the software itself, the libraries it consists of as well as its main program. Finally, we briefly describe the resulting output file.

1.2 Planet Formation

The recent theoretical framework of planet formation assumes that most planets form in the earlier stages of the formation of their parent stars, while the circumstellar disks, from which the stars are accreting their mass, are still rich in both dust and gas (e.g. Johansen et al. 2014; Pfalzner et al. 2015; Johansen & Lambrechts 2017). These circumstellar disks, observed around young stars during the first few million years of their evolution, are the result of the process within which the diffuse gas ($n \sim 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) a star accretes its mass from, can lose its high angular momentum and so collapse in stellar densities ($n \sim 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) (e.g. Shu et al. 1987). As such, the circumstellar disks, also called protoplanetary disks, have their initial size, mass and chemical composition set from their surrounding formation environment. Their subsequent evolution is shaped by the stellar radiation, the ongoing gas accretion process and the radial drift of the dust due to aerodynamic drag, and the interplay of these processes defines the environment in which planets form. In GroMiT the physical environment of the circumstellar disk is described using the equations for viscously evolving disks from Armitage 2020, which can be found in Section 2.4.4.

In the pebble accretion planet formation models, it is assumed that circumstellar disks are rich in large dust grains (e.g. mm-cm or even larger) that are generally referred to as pebbles. In this scenario it is assumed, consistently with meteoritic data from the Solar System (e.g. Lichtenberg et al. 2022), that planetesimals with size of a few hundreds of km can be formed from the dust (e.g. Johansen & Lambrechts 2017 and references therein) and these are the seeds for future planets (giants and terrestrial). These seeds act as the centre point to accrete the dust flux that surrounds them and as such undergo a continuous growth whose rate is determined by the local conditions of the disk environment (e.g. Johansen et al. 2019). Once the growing core of the forming planet reaches a certain mass, called isolation mass, it is able to perturb the gas of the disk, creating dust

traps and blocking the dust flux from reaching the planet. Therefore the mass growth of the planet effectively stalls. GroMiT adopts the treatment from Johansen et al. (2019) complemented with additional equations from Lambrechts et al. 2014, Lambrechts & Johansen (2014) and Lambrechts et al. (2014) to describe the pebble flux, the pebble accretion and the migration of the planet at this stage.

Following Johansen et al. (2019), we define the protoplanet growth rate from pebble accretion as a function of the initial size of the planetary seed. If the accretion radius of the seed is larger than the scale-height of the pebbles in the midplane of the disk, the seed growth is governed by the so-called 2D Hill regime and the mass growth rate is defined as:

$$\dot{M} = 2 \left(\frac{St}{0.1} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \Omega R_H^2 \Sigma_p$$

where M is the proto-planet mass, $St = \Omega \tau_f$ the Stokes number of the pebbles, Ω the Keplerian frequency, τ_f the friction time of the pebble, R_H the Hill radius of the protoplanet and Σ_p the pebble surface density. If the accretion radius of the planetary seed is smaller than the pebble scale-height, the seed intercepts a smaller fraction of the pebble flux and its growth takes place in the less efficient 3D Hill regime, where the Bondi radius instead. The type-I migration that occurs during this growth phase is then described by (see Eq. 2 in Johansen et al., 2019):

$$\dot{r} = - k_{mig} \frac{M}{M_{star}} \frac{\Sigma_g r^2}{M_{star}} \left(\frac{H}{r} \right)^{-2} v_K$$

where \dot{r} is the migration speed of the proto-planet, M_{star} is the host stellar mass, Σ_g the gas surface density, H/r the disk aspect ratio and v_K the Keplerian speed at the position of the planet, and k_{mig} is given from 3D numerical simulations to be $2x(1.36+0.62\beta+0.43\zeta)$ following D'Angelo & Lubow (2010).

When the planet mass reaches the isolation mass the planet is effectively cut off from the pebble flux (see Johansen et al. 2019 and references therein) and its growth is determined by its accretion of the gas in the disk. Initially this is due to the contraction of the gas in the gravitational sphere of influence of the planet, which is governed by the Kelvin-Helmholtz timescale. The isolation mass is defined as:

$$M_{iso}(r) = M_{iso,0} \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^{\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)(1-\zeta)}$$

Following Tanaka et al. (2020), after reaching the isolation mass the planet accretes mass as:

$$\frac{dM_{p,KH}}{dt} \simeq \frac{M_p}{\tau_{KH}}$$

where

$$\tau_{KH} = 1 \times 10^3 \left(\frac{M_p}{30 M_{\oplus}} \right)^{-2.5} \left(\frac{\kappa}{0.05 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}} \right) \text{ yr}$$

The mass growth in this phase is relatively slow compared to the previous one. At this point the planet starts carving a gap also in the gas. If the mass of the forming planet grows larger than the gap transition mass, M_{gap} , that Johansen et al. (2019) defined as the mass for which $K=1/0.04$, where

$$K = \left(\frac{M}{M_{\text{star}}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{H}{r} \right)^{-5} \alpha_v^{-1}$$

then the planet enters the rapid gas accretion phase. Following Tanaka et al. (2020) we define the growth rate of the planet during the runaway gas accretion as

$$\dot{M}_p = \frac{D' \pi v(r_p)}{1 + D' \pi v(r_p)} (\dot{M}_d - \dot{M}_w)$$

where

$$D' = \frac{D}{1 + 0.04K} \text{ and } D = 0.19 \left(\frac{M_p}{M_{\text{star}}} \right)^{\frac{4}{3}} \left(\frac{h_p}{r_p} \right)^{-2} r_p^2 \Omega_p$$

and \dot{M}_d and \dot{M}_w are the disk accretion rate and the mass loss rate due to photoevaporation (their difference resulting in the next influx of gas in the orbital region of the planet). The migration of the planet then follows the Type-II migration that is given by (Kanegawa et al. 2018, Tanaka et al. 2020):

$$\frac{d}{dt} \ln r_p = - 6.0 \frac{M_p}{M_{\text{star}}} \left(\frac{h_p}{r_p} \right)^{-2} \frac{r_p^2 \Sigma_{\text{gap}}}{M_{\text{star}}} \Omega_p$$

2. Software description

The GroMiT code is developed in Python 3.9 and consists of the following four .py files and two text files:

- GroMiT_initial_parameters.py: this module contains all the initial parameters that a user can modify to set the physical characteristics of the star, circumstellar disk and planet-forming environment to be simulated.
- GroMiT_constants.py: this module contains the library of physical and numerical constants that the software uses
- GroMiT_equations.py: this module contains the library of the equations that set up the circumstellar disk physical characteristics.
- GroMiT.py: the main program that calls upon the previous 3 auxiliary libraries to calculate the planet growth and migration tracks and write the output file.
- requirements.txt
- LICENSE

2.1 Python Modules required

GroMiT requires the following three Python modules to run:

Imported python modules	
Module	Notes
matplotlib	J. D. Hunter, "Matplotlib: A 2D Graphics Environment", Computing in Science & Engineering, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 90-95, 2007
numpy	Harris, C.R., Millman, K.J., van der Walt, S.J. et al. <i>Array programming with NumPy</i> . Nature 585, 357–362 (2020). DOI: 10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2 . (Publisher link).
pandas	The pandas development team. (2023). pandas-dev/pandas: Pandas (v2.1.1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8364959

2.2 Version

The current version of the program is 1.0. The authors used Spyder v5.1.5 to develop this software.

2.3 Licence

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This software is provided ‘as is’ upon request to the corresponding author and without any express or implied warranties. Commercial use is prohibited. Redistribution of the source code is subject to the express agreement of the copyright holder. Any material/publication using results from this code is required to acknowledge the software and its authors.

2.4 Usage

To run GroMiT, first download the GroMiT software package in a folder and uncompress it. This will create the six files that are described at the beginning of Section 2, plus a copy of this user guide. Make sure Python 3 is available in the system and that all the Python modules in Section 2.1 are installed.

2.4.1 Run GroMiT in an IDE

The user can load the GroMiT files in the Python v3.9 integrated development environment (IDE) of their choice (e.g. but not limited to Spyder, IDLE, Eclipse-PyDev, Sublime Text or Visual Studio Code). They can set up the values of the input parameters modifying the `GroMiT_initial_parameters.py` auxiliary file (see Section 2.4.3 for a detailed description of the file) and then press the ‘Run’ button in the IDE to compile the software. In the console provided by the IDE then type **import GroMiT** and press enter. To run GroMiT type **GroMiT.main()** and press enter as shown in Figure 1.


```

Python 3.9.12 (main, Apr 5 2022, 06:56:58)
Type "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.

IPython 8.4.0 -- An enhanced Interactive Python.

In [1]: runfile('/home/Work/Programs/GroMiT/GroMiT.py', wdir='/home/Work/Programs/GroMiT')

In [2]: import GroMiT

In [3]: GroMiT.main()
Initial semimajor axis of the planetary seed: 25.0 au

Tracking stopped by user at t= 5.0 Myrs

Warning
Figures now render in the Plots pane by default. To make them also appear inline in the
Console, uncheck "Mute Inline Plotting" under the Plots pane options menu.

Final planetary mass reached, Mp= 358.7806111801983 in units of Earth massess
Finaly semimajor axis of the planet, r= 2.5622924697660645 au
Out[3]: 0

In [4]: |

```

Figure 1: Example of running GroMiT in an IDE.

2.4.2 Run GroMiT in a Python console

The user should first open and modify the GroMiT_initial_parameters.py auxiliary file (see section 2.2.3 for a detailed description of the file). Then, open a python console in the work directory path where the GroMiT files are saved, import and run GroMiT as shown in figure 2 below.


```

IPython: GroMiT
File Edit View Search Terminal Help

Python 3.9.12 (main, Apr 5 2022, 06:56:58)
Type 'copyright', 'credits' or 'license' for more information
IPython 8.4.0 -- An enhanced interactive Python. type '?' for help.

In [1]: import GroMiT

In [2]: GroMiT.main()
Initial semimajor axis of the planetary seed: 25.0 au

Tracking stopped by user at t= 5.0 Myrs
Final planetary mass reached, Mp= 358.7806111801983 in units of Earth massess
Finaly semimajor axis of the planet, r= 2.5622924697660645 au
Out[2]: 0

In [3]: |

```

Figure 2: Example of running GroMiT in a python terminal.

2.4.3 Set the Initial Parameters

The user should first set the initial parameters needed for the program to run and that can be found in the GroMiT_initial_parameters.py auxiliary file (see Figure 3 for an example). This is the only file that needs to be modified to successfully run GroMiT. Below we briefly explain these parameters as well as give a set of default values. Running GroMiT with the default parameters will result in the plot shown Figure 5.

```

1  #!/usr/bin/python3
2  """*****
3                                     Initial Parameters
4  -----
5  All the input parameters required by the GroMiT software.
6  Modify as needed.
7
8  Written by Danae Polychroni (09/2023) v1.0.0|
9  *****
10 import GroMiT_constants as gc
11
12 """***** SET FILE NAME *****"""
13 wdir='/work/directory/path/example/'
14 file_name='GroMiT.out'
15 plot_name='GroMiT.png'
16
17 """***** SET TIME VARIABLES *****"""
18 dt=100.0*gc.YEAR          ##(sec) time step for out
19 tyear0=0.0                ##(yr) start of tracing the tracks
20 t=tyear0*gc.YEAR          ##(sec) time
21 tstop=5.e6*gc.YEAR        ##(sec) time to stop tracing the tracks
22

```

Figure 3: Example of the GroMiT_Initial_Parameters auxiliary file.

Working paths and file names inputs			
Parameter			
wdir	Set the working directory path where the GroMiT files are saved		
file_name	Set the output file name		
plot_name	Set the output plot file name		
Time Variables			
Parameter	Units	Default	
dt	years	100.0	Set the time step the main program uses in resolving the planet formation process and in the output
tyear0	years	0.0	Set the starting time of the process w.r.t. the life of the circumstellar disk
tstop	years	$5. \cdot 10^6$	Set the time to stop the process
Star and Planet Variables			
Mstar	M_{\odot}	1.0	Stellar mass
MdotPhotoev	M_{\odot}/yr	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-9}$	Mass loss due to Photoevaporation
Mcore	M_{Earth}	0.01	Mass of the solid core of the planet (initial value: mass of the planetary seed)
Menv	M_{Earth}	0.0	Mass of the gaseous envelope of the planet (default value defines an atmosphereless seed)
r	au	25.0	Orbital distance of the planet from the host star (initial value defines the starting orbit of the planetary seed)
Disk Variables			

R0	au	50.0	Characteristic radius of the disk
T0	K	200.0	Temperature of the disk and 1 au
sigma_g0_sdens	kg/m ²	420.0	Gas surface density at the characteristic radius R0
sdens_exp		0.8	Exponent of surface density profile
zeta		0.5	Exponent of power law of temperature
X			Local metallicity of the disk (value is defined as a function of the gas to dust ratio and the local temperature)
gamma		0.001	α -disk parameter
alpha3		0.0001	α -disk parameter (see Johansen et al. 2019 for a description of the physical meaning)
alphav		0.01	α -disk parameter (see Johansen et al. 2019 for a description of the physical meaning)
alpha		0.01	α -disk parameter (see Johansen et al. 2019 for a description of the physical meaning)
Dust Variables			
g2d		100.0	Gas to dust ratio
pebble_size	m	0.001	Dust or pebble size in the disk
kappa	cm ² /gr	0.05	Opacity value of the planetary envelope (Tanaka et al. 2020)
kappa0	cm ² /gr	0.05	Reference opacity value of the planetary envelope (Tanaka et al. 2020)
delta		0.0001	Dimensionless dust diffusion coefficient
water_and_organics_snowline	K	1200.	Sublimation temperature of water and organic carbon
silicate_snowline	K	1200.0	Sublimation temperature of silicates
dens_rock	kg/m ³	3000.0	Density of rock
dens_ice	kg/m ³	1000.0	Density of ice
Migration Parameters			
Kmig			Migration parameter from Johnsen et al. 2019
Plot Growth and Migration Tracks			
Parameter	Default		
x_axis_min	1.0		x-axis minimum value for plotting the resulting tracks
x_axis_max	50.0		x-axis maximum value for plotting the resulting tracks
y_axis_min	0.1		y-axis minimum value for plotting the resulting tracks
y_axis_max	700.0		y-axis maximum value for plotting the resulting tracks

2.4.4 Library of Constants

The auxiliary file GroMiT_equations.py contains all the constants that are used through the GroMiT programs. These are split into physical constants, that can be found in the table below, and *numerical* constants that are used for the optimisation of the program.

Library of physical constants		
Constant	Unit	
k	J/K	Boltzman constant
Msol	kg	Solar mass
EarthM	kg	Earth mass
mH	kg	Atomic hydrogen mass
mmw		Mean molecular weight w.r. to the number of hydrogen molecules
SQARSCTSR		Number of steradians in arcseconds squared
AU	m	Astronomical unit
G	Nm ²	Gravitational constant
DAY	sec	An earth day in seconds
YEAR	sec	An earth year in seconds

2.4.5 Auxiliary Equations Used

The main program of GroMiT calls upon the GroMiT_equations.py auxiliary file for the equations that set up the physical parameters of the circumstellar disk. These equations are listed in the table below:

Library of Auxiliary Equations	
Disk temperature	$T_r = T_0^z$
Speed of sound	$C_s = \frac{T_r}{\mu m_H}$
Keplerian Velocity	$V_K = \sqrt{\frac{GM_{star}}{r}}$
Hills radius (2D regime)	$R_H = \left(\frac{M_{planet}}{3 * M_{star}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} r$
Omega	$\Omega = V_K / r$
Scale Height	$H_r = C_s / V_K$
Kinematic viscosity of an α -disk	$\nu = \alpha C_s^2 \frac{r}{V_K}$
Characteristic Timescale	$T_c = \frac{R_c^2}{3v_{R_0} (2-\gamma)^2}$

Gas drift velocity	$v_{gas\ drift} = -\frac{3}{2} * v$
Mass accretion rate of a star	$\dot{M}_0 = -\pi R_c \Sigma_{0\ gas\ density} v_{gas\ drift}$

2.4.6 GroMiT.py

GroMiT.py contains the main body of the program. It uses several python modules (see Section 2.1) as well as the auxiliary GroMiT files described above. The **main()** program starts by initialising the input parameters and uses them to calculate the physical parameters of the circumstellar disk accordingly. Running through a loop over the user defined temporal interval (in Myrs) it calculates the mass accretion onto the star, the pebble accretion, the surface density of the pebbles, the stokes number, the radial drifts of particles and the pebble isolation mass. Through several if/else statements, the program calculates the core accretion (phase I of planet growth) onto a forming planet, its type I migration, envelope contraction (phase 1.5 of planet growth), the rapid gas accretion phase (phase II of planet growth) and updates all relevant values per time step.

Figure 4: Flow Chart of GroMiT

It, then, saves in the working directory *two* output files (called GroMiT.out and GroMiT_disk_properties.out by default; see Figure 5 for an example of the outputs). The first file contains the time step (in years) of the simulation, the initial planet seed semimajor axis (in au), the semimajor axis of the forming planet due to its migration (in au), the mass of the planet per time step (in Earth masses), the mass of the core of the forming planet per timestep (in Earth masses), the mass of the envelope of the forming planet per time step (in Earth masses), the mass accretion rate (in Solar masses per year) and the pebble isolation mass (in Earth masses). The second output file records the parameters the user chose to initialise the circumstellar disk.

```

File Edit View Search Tools Documents Help
[Icons]
GroMiT.out x
2824900.000000 25.00000000 4.0220 10.79551 10.10024 0.74195 3.806216e-09 2824900.00000 10.083724070701000
2825000.000000 25.00000000 4.0219 10.84219 10.10024 0.74195 3.806216e-09 2825000.00000 10.088447117502035
2825100.000000 25.00000000 4.0213 10.92732 10.10024 0.82708 3.806035e-09 2825100.00000 10.087163970407465
2825200.000000 25.00000000 4.0206 11.01482 10.10024 0.91458 3.805855e-09 2825200.00000 10.08587453365212
2825300.000000 25.00000000 4.0199 11.10480 10.10024 1.00455 3.805674e-09 2825300.00000 10.08457870065567
2825400.000000 25.00000000 4.0192 11.19737 10.10024 1.09713 3.805493e-09 2825400.00000 10.083276362025336

```

Figure 5: Cut out example of the Gromit.out output file

Finally, it plots the migration of the forming planet versus its accreting mass, as well as the pebble isolation mass, all in the log scale. This plot is saved in a .png file (by default called GroMiT.png) in the working directory (see Figure 6 for an example).

Figure 6: Example of a GroMiT output of a planet mass and its migration track. The blue line tracks the planet in time and the orange line is the pebble isolation mass.

3. History

1.0.0 Using the GroMiT software

- Set up output files

0.4.5 Bug fixing

0.4.0 Introducing updated mass accretion rate onto the star treatment

0.3.1 Bug fixing

0.3.0 Introduce the Tanaka et al. (2020) treatment of Kelvin-Helmholtz envelope contraction phase

0.2.1 Bug fixing

0.2.0 Introducing photoevaporation treatment

0.1.0 Original version

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5. Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Dr. Romolo Politi for his comments and suggestions on the manuscript. D. P. acknowledges the support from the Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e Geofisica Sperimentale (OGS) and CINECA through the program “HPC-TRES (High Performance Computing Training and Research for Earth Sciences)” award number 2022-05. The authors also acknowledge the support of the ASI-INAF agreement n. 2021-5-HH.1-2022.